

VISUALIZING MONITORING DATA THROUGH BIM

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Supervisors

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Abstract

One of the fields that lately has gained a lot of value in the construction market is Facility Management (FM), with a special focus on building performance. The spread of Building Information Modelling (BIM) use, as a methodology for the management of the construction processes, will bring more to a digitalized asset management. Taking a step further, the concept of Digital Twin (DT) is being used to integrate building assets with digital technologies to allow real-time analysis, as well as provide simulation possibilities. DT is expected to have a high impact on facilitating sustainable transition through technological developments, according to the European Green Deal mission.

The integration of BIM with real-time data from the Internet of Things (IoT) devices presents a powerful paradigm. This technology could create a shared data environment for cross management of building data and energy aspects. Equipping the building with monitoring systems means that a large amount of collectible data, about the indoor environment, needs to be monitored and interpreted by facility managers. The integration of the sensor data, derived from multiple sensors, into the BIM model, allows to automatically combine the monitored data with the related geometrical space in the model. Nevertheless, integrating and visualizing this monitoring IoT data in BIM is rarely seamless and is done with high dependence on the local server using native BIM authoring tools.

This research describes an attempt to develop a DT using the cloud-based platform Autodesk Forge to not only integrate and visualize real-time indoor monitoring sensor data into a BIM model but to also display a decision-making dashboard of indoor thermal comfort using the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV) index in comparison to green building benchmark standards to support complex decisions as a significantly improved alternative compared to the traditional

ways. The proposed framework is tested and verified on the case study of a school, within the project "SINCRO".

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-SylviaAkro-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/kf_Ao2b36HY

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